

1 A pseudo-transient-based staggered algorithm for hydraulic
2 fracturing simulations in the absence of a fluid lag

3 Damián Smilovich^a, Mauro Baldini^a, Humberto M. Celleri^a, Julieta Gutiérrez^{a,b}, Isaías
4 Gallana^a, Marcos F. Castez^a, Santiago Serebrinsky^a

5 ^a*YPF Tecnología S.A. (Y-TEC), Av. del Petróleo Argentino S/N, 1923, Berisso, Argentina*

6 ^b*Consejo Nacional de Investigaciones Científicas y Técnicas (CONICET), Godoy Cruz 2290, 1425,
7 CABA, Argentina*

8 **Abstract**

In the present work we propose a novel approach to the simulation of fluid-driven fracture propagation in the absence of a fluid lag. The presented algorithm relies on a staggered treatment of the coupling between the fluid and solid equations describing the viscous fluid flow driving the solid deformation and fracture propagation, allowing the use of optimal solution techniques for each individual problem. Standard finite elements are employed for the discretization of the fluid equation while a hybrid Discontinuous Galerkin/cohesive zone model formulation is chosen for modeling the solid response. Under zero fluid lag conditions, coalescence of the fluid and fracture fronts results in a Neumann elliptic boundary value problem for the fluid, exhibiting non-uniqueness as well as potentially being ill-posed. We show how a false-transient treatment of the fluid equation enables the prescription of full Neumann boundary conditions without the need to resort to intermediate pressure boundary conditions, owing to the coupling with the solid problem. Stability and convergence conditions are derived under simplifying hypotheses. The performance of the algorithm is verified against known analytical solutions, with very good results.

9 *Keywords:* Staggered simulation, fluid-driven fracture propagation, Discontinuous
10 Galerkin, cohesive zone model, false-transient, stability

11 1. Introduction

12 Several engineering applications rely on fluid-driven fracturing techniques. For in-
13 stance, oil and gas recovery from unconventional resources, such as shales, benefit from
14 the use of such techniques, as they enhance the hydraulic conductivity thus allowing
15 for an economically viable production [Valko and Economides \(1996\)](#). Hydraulic fractur-
16 ing also plays an important role in enhanced geothermal energy systems development,
17 geologic carbon sequestration, and radioactive waste disposal [Kneafsey et al. \(2018\)](#);
18 [Zimmermann and Reinicke \(2010\)](#); [Adams et al. \(2013\)](#).

19 Observation of phenomena related to the application of fluid-driven fractures in the
20 subsurface is often expensive, or even not feasible. Thus, the industry demands access
21 to robust, reliable, and scalable computational tools to simulate hydraulic fracturing
22 processes.

23 During recent years, several numerical methods have been developed or evolved to
24 simulate the response of fractured bodies upon various forms of loading. The most
25 popular methods include the Discrete Element Method (DEM) [Zhou \(2016\)](#); [Basirat
26 et al. \(2019\)](#), the Displacement Discontinuity Method (DDM) [Kresse et al. \(2013\)](#); [Ye
27 et al. \(2018\)](#) and the Finite Element Method (FEM) [Hughes \(2012\)](#). In particular, the
28 FEM allows for features to deal with the peculiarities associated with fractured bodies.
29 *E.g.*, the extended Finite Element Method (xFEM) uses enriched basis functions that
30 incorporate both the discontinuous displacements across the fracture and the stress and
31 strain singularities at the fracture tip [Sheng et al. \(2018\)](#); [Valliappan et al. \(2019\)](#). The
32 Discontinuous Galerkin formulation (DG) allows for incorporating a displacement jump
33 between nodes [Noels and Radovitzky \(2008\)](#); [Radovitzky et al. \(2011\)](#). Other modelling
34 alternatives include finite volumes [Settgast et al. \(2017\)](#), continuum damage functions
35 [Wang \(2017\)](#); [Guo et al. \(2017\)](#), cohesive zone models [Dahi Taleghani et al. \(2018\)](#); [Suo
36 et al. \(2019\)](#) or a combination of FEM/DEM [Knight et al. \(2020\)](#).

37 The fracturing fluid front and the propagating crack front typically do not coincide,
38 leading to a fluid lag region between the two fronts. Nevertheless, in many cases the

39 fluid lag is negligible, and the zero-lag approximation is valid. This is the case for
40 high enough remote confining stresses, and/or high enough non-dimensional toughness
41 [Garagash \(2006\)](#); [Lecampion and Detournay \(2007\)](#). The capability of simulating under
42 zero-lag conditions is therefore of particular interest, yet numerically challenging.

43 The modeling of hydraulic fracturing in the absence of a fluid lag has been vastly
44 studied, both analytically [Garagash \(2000\)](#); [Garagash and Detournay \(2005\)](#); [Detournay](#)
45 [\(2016\)](#), and computationally [Giovanardi et al. \(2020\)](#); [Kanin et al. \(2020\)](#); [Moukhtari](#)
46 [et al. \(2020\)](#). A recent review article elaborates on the most common numerical ap-
47 proaches for tackling the general problem, and discusses their advantages and limitations
48 [Lecampion et al. \(2018\)](#).

49 In the present work, we develop an algorithm for the simulation of fluid-driven fracture
50 propagation in the absence of a fluid lag, and implement it in Y-FRAC[®], a numerical
51 framework for massively-parallel computational mechanics simulations. The simulator is
52 based on a Discontinuous Galerkin (DG) finite element formulation together with a cohe-
53 sive zone model (CZM) for modeling the crack initiation and propagation throughout the
54 solid domain [Noels and Radovitzky \(2006b,a, 2008\)](#); [Seagraves and Radovitzky \(2009\)](#);
55 [Radovitzky et al. \(2011\)](#). A similar methodology can be found in [Hirmand and Papoulia](#)
56 [\(2019\)](#); [Hirmand et al. \(2019\)](#). Inter-element displacement continuity before the onset
57 of fracture is weakly enforced by means of additional energy terms in the weak formu-
58 lation. The addition of corresponding interface elements involves node duplication, thus
59 resulting in an increased number of degrees of freedom [Noels and Radovitzky \(2006b\)](#).
60 Fractures initiate and propagate along the inter-element boundaries when a given failure
61 criterion is locally satisfied [Radovitzky et al. \(2011\)](#). As the mesh geometry dictates the
62 set of all possible crack paths, fine enough meshes are required in order to produce a
63 well-converged result, in a sense that includes the propagation path.

64 As customary, we describe the viscous fluid flow along the fractures with the Reynolds
65 lubrication equation [Batchelor \(2000\)](#). The fluid domain is constructed such that its
66 support is the set of all solid interface elements. Under the assumption of small defor-

67 mations, the channel opening is obtained directly from the corresponding displacement
68 jump projected along the element normal.

69 The staggered solution algorithm is enabled by a false-transient [Northrop et al. \(2013\)](#)
70 treatment of the fluid equation, allowing for the prescription of full Neumann boundary
71 conditions, which would otherwise lead to an ill-posed problem and multiple solutions for
72 the original elliptic equation. An added fictitious pseudo-time dependent term produces
73 a parabolic equation that leads to the sought-for steady state solution, provided mass
74 conservation is fulfilled. **Other authors employ intermediate boundary conditions in order
75 to circumvent this issue [Vahab and Khalili \(2019\)](#). This technique involves replacing the
76 injection rate boundary condition by a prescribed pressure boundary condition, and then
77 iteratively adjusting the inlet pressure until the target flow rate is attained. This leads
78 to an additional iterative loop, which we avoid.**

79 The article is organized as follows. In section [2](#) we present a brief description of
80 the governing solid and fluid equations, the coupling between them, and the respective
81 discretization schemes. Section [3](#) introduces the staggered algorithm devised for the
82 solution of the coupled problem. Stability and convergence are analyzed for a particular
83 case under simplifying hypotheses in section [4](#). In section [5](#) we test the simulator against
84 known analytical solutions in 2D and 3D, while the final conclusions are summarized in
85 section [6](#).

86 **2. Governing equations and discretization schemes**

87 In what follows we review the equations governing the quasi-static propagation of
88 cracks in an impermeable brittle elastic solid medium, driven by the injection of a viscous
89 incompressible fluid. The discretization schemes that lead to the resulting discrete weak
90 formulations are introduced, and a strongly nonlinear coupling is shown to exist between
91 the two equations. Afterwards, we elaborate on the chosen criterion for the development
92 of further crack propagation.

93 2.1. Solid equations

Let $\mathcal{B}_s \subset \mathbb{R}^d$, $d = 2, 3$, be the solid domain, and $\Gamma \subset \partial\mathcal{B}_s$ the crack region boundary. Additionally, let $\partial\mathcal{B}_N, \partial\mathcal{B}_D \subset \partial\mathcal{B}_s$ be the Neumann and Dirichlet boundaries, such that $\partial\mathcal{B}_N \cup \partial\mathcal{B}_D \cup \Gamma = \partial\mathcal{B}_s$, $\partial\mathcal{B}_N \cap \Gamma = \emptyset$, $\partial\mathcal{B}_D \cap \Gamma = \emptyset$, $\partial\mathcal{B}_N \cap \partial\mathcal{B}_D = \emptyset$. The solid equilibrium equations are then given by

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{ll} \nabla \cdot \boldsymbol{\sigma} = -\rho \mathbf{b} & \text{in } \mathcal{B} \quad , \\ \boldsymbol{\sigma} \cdot \mathbf{n} = -p \mathbf{n} & \text{on } \Gamma \quad , \\ \boldsymbol{\sigma} \cdot \mathbf{n} = \tilde{\mathbf{t}} & \text{on } \partial\mathcal{B}_N \quad , \\ \mathbf{u} = \tilde{\mathbf{u}} & \text{on } \partial\mathcal{B}_D \quad , \end{array} \right. \quad (1)$$

94 in which $\boldsymbol{\sigma}$ is the Cauchy stress tensor, ρ the material density, \mathbf{b} the body forces, and \mathbf{u}
 95 the displacement vector field. The solid is subjected to a remote stress field $\tilde{\boldsymbol{\sigma}}$ dictating
 96 the traction $\tilde{\mathbf{t}} = \tilde{\boldsymbol{\sigma}} \cdot \mathbf{n}$ applied on the Neumann boundary $\partial\mathcal{B}_N$, while the displacement
 97 field $\tilde{\mathbf{u}}$ is prescribed along the Dirichlet boundary $\partial\mathcal{B}_D$. Similarly, the subset of the
 98 boundary corresponding to the crack faces, Γ , is subjected to a fluid pressure loading
 99 boundary condition, given by p . In all of the preceding, \mathbf{n} is the outer unit normal
 100 vector. We assume linear elasticity and infinitesimal strains, so that $\boldsymbol{\sigma} = \mathbf{C} : \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}$, with \mathbf{C}
 101 the fourth rank elasticity tensor, and $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}$ the infinitesimal strain tensor which is related to
 102 the displacements through $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}(\mathbf{u}) = \frac{1}{2}(\nabla \mathbf{u} + \nabla \mathbf{u}^T)$.

The fluid-driven fracture propagation and associated energy dissipation process is modeled by means of a cohesive zone model [Dugdale \(1960\)](#); [Radovitzky et al. \(2011\)](#), which endows the cohesive process zone with a traction-separation law (TSL) $\mathbf{T} = \mathbf{T}(\boldsymbol{\Delta}, \mathbf{q})$. This constitutive behaviour relates the separation $\boldsymbol{\Delta}$ and the traction \mathbf{T} across the faces of the cohesive zone, incorporating a suitable set \mathbf{q} of internal variables, which have their corresponding hardening laws. In terms of the normal and tangential compo-

nents, we have

$$\mathbf{\Delta} = \Delta_n \mathbf{n} + \Delta_m \mathbf{m} \quad , \quad (2)$$

$$\mathbf{T} = T_n \mathbf{n} + T_m \mathbf{m} \quad . \quad (3)$$

We further specialize to an effective TSL $T(\delta, \mathbf{q})$ between an effective traction T and an effective separation $\delta = \sqrt{\Delta_n^2 + \gamma^2 \Delta_m^2}$, also including \mathbf{q} , where γ is the mode weighting factor [Ortiz and Pandolfi \(1999\)](#). This typically implies that \mathbf{T} can be derived from a potential, and

$$\mathbf{T} = \frac{T}{\delta} (\Delta_n \mathbf{n} + \gamma^2 \Delta_m \mathbf{m}) \quad . \quad (4)$$

For the effective TSL we choose the usual linear softening irreversible law

$$T(\delta, \delta_{\max}) = \begin{cases} \sigma_c \left(1 - \frac{\delta}{\delta_c}\right) & \text{if } \dot{\delta} \geq 0 \text{ and } \delta = \delta_{\max} \quad , \\ \sigma_c \left(1 - \frac{\delta_{\max}}{\delta_c}\right) \frac{\delta}{\delta_{\max}} & \text{if } \dot{\delta} < 0 \text{ or } \delta < \delta_{\max} \quad . \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

Here, σ_c is the critical stress for which the TSL becomes operational, and δ_c is the separation beyond which there is no further traction between the crack faces. The resulting fracture energy is

$$G_c = \frac{1}{2} \sigma_c \delta_c \quad . \quad (6)$$

103 2.2. Solid discretization

104 Let \mathcal{B}_h be the reference computational domain and $\{\mathcal{B}_h^e\}_{e=1, \dots, N_e}$ a partition of \mathcal{B}_h , so
 105 that $\bigcup_{e=1}^{N_e} \mathcal{B}_h^e = \mathcal{B}_h$ and $\mathcal{B}_h^{n \circ} \cap \mathcal{B}_h^{m \circ} = \emptyset$ for all $n \neq m$, where \bullet° denotes set-interior. This
 106 partition induces an internal boundary that we will identify as $\partial_I \mathcal{B}_h = \bigcup_{e=1}^{N_e} \partial \mathcal{B}_h^e \setminus \partial \mathcal{B}_h$.
 107 Similarly, let $\{\partial_I \mathcal{B}_h^i\}_{i=1, \dots, N_i}$ be a partition of $\partial_I \mathcal{B}_h$, satisfying $\bigcup_{i=1}^{N_i} \partial_I \mathcal{B}_h^i = \partial_I \mathcal{B}_h$ and
 108 $\partial_I \mathcal{B}_h^{n \circ} \cap \partial_I \mathcal{B}_h^{m \circ} = \emptyset$ for all $n \neq m$.

We approximate the displacement vector field \mathbf{u} as $\mathbf{u}_h = \sum_{i=1}^{n_u} u_i \boldsymbol{\varphi}_i$, where $\{\boldsymbol{\varphi}_i\}_{i=1, \dots, n_u}$ is a given basis of the usual Discontinuous Galerkin finite element interpolation space

\mathbf{u}_h , with

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{u}_h &= \mathcal{U}_h^d \quad , \\ \mathcal{U}_h &= \left\{ v_h \in \mathcal{L}^2(\mathcal{B}_h) : v_h|_{\mathcal{B}_h^e} \in \mathcal{P}^k(\mathcal{B}_h^e) \quad \forall \mathcal{B}_h^e \subset \mathcal{B}_h, \quad e = 1, \dots, N_e \right\} \quad . \end{aligned}$$

109 In the preceding definition, \bullet^d stands for d -ary Cartesian product, $\mathcal{L}^2(\mathcal{B}_h)$ is the
 110 space of square-integrable functions over \mathcal{B}_h , and $\mathcal{P}^k(\mathcal{B}_h^e)$ is the space of polynomials of
 111 degree at most k with support in \mathcal{B}_h^e . The elements \mathbf{v}_h of \mathbf{u}_h are allowed to be jump-
 112 discontinuous in \mathcal{B}_h . They only need to satisfy the essential boundary conditions and be
 113 square-integrable [Noels and Radovitzky \(2006b\)](#).

114 The stabilized and discretized weak formulation for the solid problem can now be
 115 obtained by testing equation (1) against \mathbf{v}_h , $\forall \mathbf{v}_h \in \mathbf{u}_h$, and integrating over the entire
 116 domain \mathcal{B}_h

$$\begin{aligned} & \sum_{e=1}^{N_e} \int_{\mathcal{B}_h^e} (\mathcal{C} : \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}(\mathbf{u}_h)) : \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}(\mathbf{v}_h) \, d\Omega \\ & - \int_{\mathcal{B}_h^e} \rho \mathbf{b} \cdot \mathbf{v}_h \, d\Omega \\ & - \int_{\partial \mathcal{B}_h^e \cap \partial \mathcal{B}_{h,N}} \tilde{\mathbf{t}} \cdot \mathbf{v}_h \, d\Gamma \\ & + \sum_{i=1}^{N_i} \int_{\partial_t \mathcal{B}_h^i} (1 - \alpha) \llbracket \mathbf{u}_h \rrbracket \cdot \langle \mathcal{C} : \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}(\mathbf{v}_h) \rangle \cdot \mathbf{n} \, d\Gamma \\ & + \int_{\partial_t \mathcal{B}_h^i} (1 - \alpha) (\llbracket \mathbf{u}_h \rrbracket \otimes \mathbf{n}) : \left\langle \frac{\beta_s}{h_s} \mathcal{C} \right\rangle : (\llbracket \mathbf{v}_h \rrbracket \otimes \mathbf{n}) \, d\Gamma \\ & + \int_{\partial_t \mathcal{B}_h^i} \alpha (\mathbf{T}(\delta) - p \mathbf{n}) \cdot \llbracket \mathbf{v}_h \rrbracket \, d\Gamma = 0 \quad \forall \mathbf{v}_h \in \mathbf{u}_h \quad , \end{aligned} \tag{7}$$

117 where $\llbracket \bullet \rrbracket \stackrel{def}{=} \bullet^+ - \bullet^-$ is the jump operator, and $\langle \bullet \rangle \stackrel{def}{=} \frac{1}{2} (\bullet^+ + \bullet^-)$ is the average
 118 operator.

119 The first and second terms in equation (7) take into consideration the contribution
 120 from the bulk stresses and body forces. The third term includes the remote traction
 121 boundary conditions in (1) over the Neumann boundary of the computational domain.

122 The next two terms emerge from the Discontinuous Galerkin discretization as the con-
 123 sistency and stabilization terms, respectively, the latter of which involves the DG stabi-
 124 lization parameter β_s and a measure h_s of the mesh size. In the absence of fracture, the
 125 stabilization term weakly enforces the displacement continuity across the inter-element
 126 boundaries [Noels and Radovitzky \(2006b\)](#) by virtue of interface elements. The parameter
 127 α dictates whether the contribution of the different terms is to be taken into account,
 128 taking the value 1 if the failure criterion has been met, and 0 otherwise. As α takes the
 129 value 1, the consistency and stabilization terms are dropped and the last term carrying
 130 the contribution from the TSL and the external fluid pressure becomes active.

131 2.3. Fluid equations

Let $\mathcal{B}_f \subset \mathbb{R}^d$, $d = 2, 3$, be the fluid domain, and $\bar{\Gamma}$ the middle crack surface. The fluid
 entirely fills the cracks so that $\partial\mathcal{B}_f = \bar{\Gamma}$. Let us denote the crack opening normal to $\bar{\Gamma}$ as
 w . Under the assumption that $w \ll M(\bar{\Gamma})$, with $M(\bar{\Gamma})$ a measure of the crack size, for
 instance its length in the 2D case, or its surface area in the 3D case, we may deem the
 thin-walled approximation valid [Batchelor \(2000\)](#). If we also consider laminar flow, we
 can formulate the mass conservation equation for the fluid flow inside a crack as

$$\nabla_{\bar{\Gamma}} \cdot \mathbf{q} + \frac{\partial w}{\partial t} + \frac{2C_L}{\sqrt{t - t_0(\mathbf{x})}} - \mathcal{Q} = 0 \quad . \quad (8)$$

132 The first term in equation (8) corresponds to the fluid flow divergence, where the fluid
 133 flow is given in terms of the velocity \mathbf{v} and the normal crack opening by $\mathbf{q} = w\mathbf{v}$. The
 134 second term, usually called the squeeze term, refers to the opening time derivative which
 135 acts as a sink term, while the third term incorporates the fluid loss in the form of leak-off,
 136 which is modeled as a one-dimensional diffusion process as per the Carter model [Carter](#)
 137 [et al. \(2000\)](#). This gives the leak-off rate in terms of the Carter leak-off coefficient C_L ,
 138 the time t , and the fluid arrival time t_0 . This expression is only meaningful for $t > t_0$ so
 139 its contribution is otherwise taken as nil. Lastly, \mathcal{Q} accounts for the injection flow rate.

We may express the fluid velocity in terms of the pressure gradient by means of the

Poiseuille law

$$\mathbf{v} = -\frac{w^2}{12\mu} \nabla_{\bar{\Gamma}} p \quad , \quad (9)$$

which in combination with (8) yields the Reynolds lubrication equation

$$\nabla_{\bar{\Gamma}} \cdot \left(\frac{w^3 \nabla_{\bar{\Gamma}} p}{12\mu} \right) - \frac{\partial w}{\partial t} - \frac{2C_L}{\sqrt{t-t_0(\mathbf{x})}} + \mathcal{Q} = 0 \quad \text{in } \bar{\Gamma} \quad . \quad (10)$$

140 In the above equations, $\nabla_{\bar{\Gamma}}$ is the tangential gradient operator on $\bar{\Gamma}$, μ is the fluid
 141 dynamic viscosity, and $\mathcal{Q} = \sum_i q_i \delta(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}_i)$, where at each injection point \mathbf{x}_i the cor-
 142 responding volume flow rate is q_i . On $\partial\bar{\Gamma}$ we prescribe zero-flow boundary conditions
 143 [Adachi et al. \(2007\)](#).

Since no Dirichlet boundary conditions are being imposed, the elliptic boundary value problem given by equation (10) is ill-posed unless the solvability condition

$$\int_{\bar{\Gamma}} \frac{\partial w}{\partial t} d\Gamma + \int_{\bar{\Gamma}} \frac{2C_L}{\sqrt{t-t_0(\mathbf{x})}} d\Gamma - \int_{\bar{\Gamma}} \mathcal{Q} d\Gamma = 0 \quad (11)$$

144 is met. The solvability condition can be physically interpreted as the global conservation
 145 of fluid volume. The instantaneous change in the overall fluid volume has to balance out
 146 the fluid volume loss coming from the leak-off term as well as the contribution from the
 147 source term. Regardless, even when the problem is well-posed, the solution is unique only
 148 up to a constant arbitrary pressure level that becomes an additional unknown [Adachi](#)
 149 [et al. \(2007\)](#) when one considers the decoupled fluid equation, as will be the case for our
 150 overall solution scheme.

151 2.4. Fluid discretization

Standard \mathcal{C}^0 finite elements are employed for the discretization of the lubrication equation (10), so that the fluid pressure scalar field p may be approximated as $p_h = \sum_{i=1}^{n_p} p_i \varphi_i$, with $\{\varphi_i\}_{i=1, \dots, n_p}$ a basis of the usual continuous Galerkin finite element

interpolation space \mathcal{P}_h given by

$$\mathcal{P}_h = \left\{ q_h \in \mathcal{C}^0(\partial_I \mathcal{B}_h) : q_h|_{\partial_I \mathcal{B}_h^i} \in \mathcal{P}^k(\partial_I \mathcal{B}_h^i) \forall \partial_I \mathcal{B}_h^i \subset \partial_I \mathcal{B}_h, i = 1, \dots, N_i \right\} ,$$

152 where $\mathcal{C}^0(\partial_I \mathcal{B}_h)$ is the space of continuous functions over $\partial_I \mathcal{B}_h$. Note that the interpola-
 153 tion order k for the approximations of \mathbf{u}_h and p_h coincides. The set of all fluid elements
 154 has the same support $\partial_I \mathcal{B}_h$ as the set of all solid interface elements, so there is a natural
 155 one-to-one geometrical correspondence between the two.

We test (10) against $q_h \forall q_h \in \mathcal{P}_h$, and integrate over $\partial_I \mathcal{B}_h$ to obtain the semi-
 discretized weak formulation for the fluid problem

$$\begin{aligned} & \sum_{i=1}^{N_i} \int_{\partial_I \mathcal{B}_h^i} \frac{w^3}{12\mu} \nabla_{\bar{\Gamma}} p_h \cdot \nabla_{\bar{\Gamma}} q_h \, d\Gamma \\ & + \int_{\partial_I \mathcal{B}_h^i} \frac{\partial w}{\partial t} q_h \, d\Gamma \\ & + \int_{\partial_I \mathcal{B}_h^i} \frac{2C_L}{\sqrt{t-t_0(\mathbf{x})}} q_h \, d\Gamma \\ & - \int_{\partial_I \mathcal{B}_h^i} \mathcal{Q} q_h \, d\Gamma = 0 \quad \forall q_h \in \mathcal{P}_h \quad . \end{aligned} \tag{12}$$

156 2.5. Fluid–solid coupling

157 Let us define $\mathbf{n}_{\bar{\Gamma}}$ as the unit normal to the middle crack surface, so that we can then
 158 introduce the discrete normal fracture opening $w_h = \llbracket \mathbf{u}_h \rrbracket \cdot \mathbf{n}_{\bar{\Gamma}}$.

159 Solving the coupled hydro-mechanical problem implies satisfying equations (7) and
 160 (12) simultaneously, where the pressure field p appearing in equation (7) as an external
 161 loading is taken to be p_h , the solution to equation (12). Similarly, the normal crack
 162 opening w in equation (12) determines the crack permeability $\frac{w^2}{12\mu}$ as well as the sink
 163 term $\frac{\partial w}{\partial t}$, and is held to be w_h , which requires knowledge of the discrete displacement
 164 field \mathbf{u}_h first in order to be computed. Furthermore, for a solution to (12) to exist, (11)
 165 must be fulfilled, while the constant pressure level remains indeterminate.

166 It is clear that a strongly nonlinear coupling exists between the two physical processes.

167 While equation (7) is linear in the unknown field p_h , the discrete normal fracture opening
 168 w_h appears raised to the third power in equation (12) as well as in the crack opening
 169 velocity sink term.

In order to track the time evolution of the system, we perform a time discretization
 whereby the sink term $\frac{\partial w_h}{\partial t}$ may be approximated as

$$\frac{\partial w_h}{\partial t} \Big|_{t_n} \approx \frac{w_h^{t_n} - w_h^{t_{n-1}}}{\Delta t} \quad , \quad (13)$$

170 where Δt is the time interval separating hydro-mechanical equilibrium states n and $n-1$,
 171 corresponding to $t = t_n$ and $t = t_{n-1}$, respectively. **For ease of notation, whenever a time**
 172 **superscript is omitted, we are referencing the corresponding variable at the current time.**
 173 **So for instance, w_h refers to $w_h^{t_n}$.**

We may now present the fully-discretized weak formulations of equation (1) at time
 $t = t_n$

$$\begin{aligned} & \sum_{e=1}^{N_e} \int_{\mathcal{B}_h^e} (\mathcal{C} : \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}(\mathbf{u}_h^{t_n})) : \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}(\mathbf{v}_h) \, d\Omega \\ & - \int_{\mathcal{B}_h^e} \rho \mathbf{b} \cdot \mathbf{v}_h \, d\Omega \\ & - \int_{\partial \mathcal{B}_h^e \cap \partial \mathcal{B}_{h,N}} \tilde{\mathbf{t}} \cdot \mathbf{v}_h \, d\Gamma \\ & + \sum_{i=1}^{N_i} \int_{\partial_I \mathcal{B}_h^i} (1 - \alpha^{t_n}) \llbracket \mathbf{u}_h^{t_n} \rrbracket \cdot \langle \mathcal{C} : \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}(\mathbf{v}_h) \rangle \cdot \mathbf{n} \, d\Gamma \\ & + \int_{\partial_I \mathcal{B}_h^i} (1 - \alpha^{t_n}) (\llbracket \mathbf{u}_h^{t_n} \rrbracket \otimes \mathbf{n}) : \left\langle \frac{\beta_s}{h_s} \mathcal{C} \right\rangle : (\llbracket \mathbf{v}_h \rrbracket \otimes \mathbf{n}) \, d\Gamma \\ & + \int_{\partial_I \mathcal{B}_h^i} (\alpha^{t_n} \mathbf{T}(\delta) - \beta^{t_n} p_h^{t_n} \mathbf{n}) \cdot \llbracket \mathbf{v}_h \rrbracket \, d\Gamma = 0 \quad \forall \mathbf{v}_h \in \mathcal{U}_h \quad , \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

and that of equation (10)

$$\begin{aligned}
& \sum_{i=1}^{N_i} \int_{\partial_I \mathcal{B}_h^i} \beta^{t_n} \frac{w_h^{t_n 3}}{12\mu} \nabla_{\Gamma} p_h^{t_n} \cdot \nabla_{\Gamma} q_h \, d\Gamma \\
& + \int_{\partial_I \mathcal{B}_h^i} \beta^{t_n} \frac{w_h^{t_n} - w_h^{t_{n-1}}}{\Delta t} q_h \, d\Gamma \\
& + \int_{\partial_I \mathcal{B}_h^i} \beta^{t_n} \frac{2C_L}{\sqrt{t_n - t_0(\mathbf{x})}} q_h \, d\Gamma \\
& - \int_{\partial_I \mathcal{B}_h^i} \mathcal{Q} q_h \, d\Gamma = 0 \quad \forall q_h \in \mathcal{P}_h \quad .
\end{aligned} \tag{15}$$

The scalar field β^t is such that its support defines the fluid domain, *i.e.*, it indicates the presence of fracturing fluid by taking the value 1 if the discrete normal fracture opening at time t is greater than a given threshold w_0 , which together with connectedness constitute the filling criteria, and 0 otherwise. Hence, we may activate or deactivate fluid elements based on this condition. Notice that imposing a minimum opening effectively removes the pressure singularity at the tip induced by the no-flow boundary condition. We choose $w_0 \ll \delta_c$ so as to allow the fluid to penetrate the cohesive zone [Giovanardi et al. \(2020\)](#). The discretized form of equation (11) is then

$$\sum_{i=1}^{N_i} \int_{\partial_I \mathcal{B}_h^i} \beta^{t_n} \frac{w_h^{t_n} - w_h^{t_{n-1}}}{\Delta t} \, d\Gamma + \int_{\partial_I \mathcal{B}_h^i} \beta^{t_n} \frac{2C_L}{\sqrt{t_n - t_0(\mathbf{x})}} \, d\Gamma - \int_{\partial_I \mathcal{B}_h^i} \mathcal{Q} \, d\Gamma = 0 \quad . \tag{16}$$

174 In section 3 we present a solution strategy aimed at simultaneously solving (14)
175 and (15) in a staggered manner at time t_n , evolving from a previous known state at
176 time t_{n-1} quasi-statically, and dealing with the solvability condition (16) and pressure
177 indeterminacy.

178 2.6. Crack propagation criterion

179 Upon the satisfaction of an adequate failure criterion, the TSL (5) becomes opera-
180 tional and energy is released as the effective crack separation increases until complete
181 fracture is attained for $\delta \geq \delta_c$. The triggering condition for this process to initiate

182 is that the effective traction $T = \sqrt{\sigma^2 + \gamma^{-2}\tau^2}$ must exceed the cohesive strength σ_c
183 [Radovitzky et al. \(2011\)](#), where σ and τ are the normal and tangential traction compo-
184 nents relative to the interface element normal \mathbf{n} . The traction vector can be written as
185 $\mathbf{t} = \boldsymbol{\sigma} \cdot \mathbf{n} = \sigma \mathbf{n} + \tau \mathbf{m}$, with $\mathbf{n} \cdot \mathbf{m} = 0$, so that $\sigma = (\boldsymbol{\sigma} \cdot \mathbf{n}) \cdot \mathbf{n}$, $\tau = \sqrt{\|\mathbf{t}\|^2 - \sigma^2}$ [Dvorkin](#)
186 [and Goldschmit \(2005\)](#).

We use a mesh size dependent failure criterion, which allows for enlarging the element size while still properly resolving the cohesive zone, therefore keeping the outcome of the simulations essentially unchanged [Turon et al. \(2007\)](#) [Smilovich et al. \(2018\)](#). The corresponding cohesive strength is given in terms of the fracture toughness K_{Ic} and a measure l of the element size as

$$\sigma_c = \frac{K_{Ic}}{\sqrt{2\pi l}} \quad . \quad (17)$$

187 3. Solution strategy

188 A staggered treatment of the coupled hydro-mechanical problem (14) and (15) has
189 been shown to become unstable under certain conditions [Giovanardi et al. \(2020\)](#) [Matin](#)
190 [and Robert \(2019\)](#). **These instabilities, which manifest themselves as an oscillatory re-**
191 **sponse in terms of the fluid pressure and the crack opening, can be dealt with, as shown**
192 **in [Smilovich et al. \(2021\)](#) through a pressure relaxation parameter, or as in [Vahab and](#)**
193 **[Khalili \(2019\)](#) where the opening profile is computed as a weighted combination of the**
194 **opening profile coming from the two previous iterations.** Regardless, the prescription of
195 full Neumann boundary conditions for the lubrication equation still leads to nonunique-
196 ness of the solution or, potentially, ill-posedness.

197 3.1. Staggered solution

198 Given the hydro-mechanical equilibrium state $n-1$ at time t_{n-1} , characterized by the
199 pair $(p_h^{t_{n-1}}, \mathbf{u}_h^{t_{n-1}})$ plus a set of fluid and solid internal variables $(\mathbf{q}_f^{t_{n-1}}, \mathbf{q}_s^{t_{n-1}})$, we seek to
200 develop a stable staggered solution scheme that leads to the simultaneous solution of

201 equations (14) and (15) at time t_n , quasi-statically evolving from the previous known
 202 state, while necessarily satisfying (16) and resolving the pressure indeterminacy.

203 Let $(p_h^{k+1}, \mathbf{u}_h^{k+1}) = \mathcal{H}(\mathbf{u}_h^k)$ be the staggered operator that advances the solution from
 204 k to $k + 1$, where k denotes the current iteration. Our goal is now to define adequate
 205 operators \mathcal{F} and \mathcal{S} such that $p_h^{k+1} = \mathcal{F}(\mathbf{u}_h^k)$ and $\mathbf{u}_h^{k+1} = \mathcal{S}(p_h^{k+1}) = \mathcal{S}(\mathcal{F}(\mathbf{u}_h^k))$, with
 206 $\mathcal{H}(\mathbf{u}_h^k) = (\mathcal{F}(\mathbf{u}_h^k), \mathcal{S}(\mathcal{F}(\mathbf{u}_h^k)))$. That is, a way to sequentially evolve the pressure field
 207 from iteration k to $k + 1$, and then obtain the displacement field at iteration $k + 1$ in
 208 terms of the updated fluid pressure field. If the staggered scheme converges we have
 209 $\mathbf{u}_h^k \xrightarrow[k \rightarrow \infty]{} \mathbf{u}_h$ and $p_h^k \xrightarrow[k \rightarrow \infty]{} p_h$ where \mathbf{u}_h and p_h simultaneously solve (14) and (15) at
 210 time $t = t_n$, where convergence is to be understood in terms of convergence of the nodal
 211 coefficients.

212 3.2. Fluid solution

Let $\mathbf{P}^k = \{P_i^k\}_{i=1, \dots, n_p}$ be the vector of nodal pressure values. Equation (15) at
 iteration $k + 1$ may then be written as the linear system of equations

$$K_{ij}^k P_j^{k+1} = Q_i^k, \quad i = 1, \dots, n_p \quad , \quad (18)$$

213 where summation over j is implied. The stiffness matrix \mathbf{K} and the nodal force vector
 214 \mathbf{Q} are both functions of the discrete normal fracture opening and are thus computed in
 215 terms of $w_h^k = \llbracket \mathbf{u}_h^k \rrbracket \cdot \mathbf{n}_\Gamma$. The force vector lumps the various source terms, such as the
 216 opening time derivative, the leak-off term, and the injection flow rate. Equation (16) will
 217 in general not be satisfied unless $\mathbf{u}_h^k = \mathbf{u}_h$, preventing a solution to (18) from existing at
 218 all, so we devise the following strategy.

219 Let us introduce the pseudo-transient term $\mathbf{P}^{k+1} - \mathbf{P}^k$, which can be thought of as
 220 a pressure time derivative in pseudo-time k .

$p_h^k \xrightarrow[k \rightarrow \infty]{} p_h$ implies that for each $i = 1, \dots, n_p$, given $\epsilon > 0$ there exists some k_0
 such that $|P_i^{k_0+1} - P_i^{k_0}| < \epsilon$, thus the pseudo-transient term effectively vanishes if the
 staggered scheme converges and the resulting pressure field p_h solves (15), while w_h

necessarily satisfies (16). Therefore, we may define \mathcal{F} as the solution to the following equations for given \mathbf{u}_h^k

$$B_{ij} \left(P_j^{k+1} - P_j^k \right) + K_{ij}^k P_j^{k+1} = Q_i^k, \quad i, j = 1, \dots, n_p \quad , \quad (19)$$

where \mathbf{B} is the artificial compressibility matrix, **which may be computed in terms of a suitable artificial compressibility parameter, the choice of which will be discussed in the next section, and the element shape functions as**

$$B_{ij} = \int_{\partial_T \mathcal{E}_h} B N_i N_j \, d\Gamma, \quad i, j = 1, \dots, n_p \quad . \quad (20)$$

221 The system of linear equations (19) can be interpreted as corresponding to an implicit
 222 Euler time-marching scheme in pseudo-time k for the artificially-parabolized lubrication
 223 equation with unit time step, with p_h being the steady-state solution that we seek. This
 224 is also known as the pseudo-transient method [Northrop et al. \(2013\)](#).

225 The resulting system of equations resembles that arising from the fixed-stress HF
 226 split [Matin \(2019\)](#), although we do not replace the opening time derivative term nor do
 227 we seek a predictor value for it. By keeping it, we preserve the mechanism that drives
 228 (19) towards a steady state response, thus avoiding the need of additional iterative loops
 229 for determining what the actual flow rate is. We emphasize that no steady-state solution
 230 to (19) exists unless (16) is fulfilled.

231 As in [Giovanardi et al. \(2020\)](#), we adopt an explicit time treatment of the fluid
 232 domain, *i.e.*, we take β in equations (15) and (16) to be $\beta^{t_{n-1}}$ and only update it after
 233 convergence has been attained, effectively fixing the fluid domain during the iterative
 234 process.

Let $\mathbf{U}^k = \{U_i^k\}_{i=1,\dots,n_u}$ be the vector of nodal displacements. Equation (14) at iteration $k + 1$ can then be written as the following system of equations

$$R_i(\mathbf{U}^{k+1}) = F_i^{ext}(\mathbf{U}^{k+1}) - F_i^{int}(\mathbf{U}^{k+1}) = 0, \quad i = 1, \dots, n_u \quad , \quad (21)$$

with \mathbf{R} being the residual force vector, which is the difference between the external forces \mathbf{F}^{ext} and the internal forces \mathbf{F}^{int} . In particular, the external force vector carries the fluid pressure load contribution from p_h^{k+1} . The above system of equations is nonlinear in \mathbf{U} due to both crack propagation and the TSL. Further causes of non-linearity arise in the form of contact due to fracture closure, and from the intricate interaction patterns that may take place between both multiple hydraulic and pre-existing natural fractures. A combination of the Dynamic Relaxation (DR) method [Underwood \(1986\)](#) [Oakley and Knight Jr \(1995\)](#) and a mass scaling technique is hence adopted as a means to robustly handle (21). The DR algorithm is based on the addition of fictitious mass and damping matrices, resulting in the following semi-discrete equations of motion

$$M_{ij} \frac{d^2 U_j}{d\tau^2} + C_{ij} \frac{dU_j}{d\tau} + F_i^{ext}(\mathbf{U}) = F_i^{int}(\mathbf{U}), \quad i, j = 1, \dots, n_u \quad , \quad (22)$$

where τ is a pseudo-time parameter governing the mechanical evolution of the system towards a static equilibrium, \mathbf{M} is the fictitious mass matrix, and \mathbf{C} is the mass damping matrix. Summation over j is again implied. We will refer to each pseudo-time advancement of (22) as a DR step, with m serving as an index for the successive steps.

We solve (22) using the explicit Newmark-beta method for a lumped mass matrix chosen in the following way: we set the fictitious density to unity and scale the element masses accordingly so that the critical time step is uniform throughout the mesh, *i.e.*, no particular element imposes a time step restriction for the time integration scheme. We have observed that including mass scaling into the DR algorithm dramatically reduces the number of iterations needed to reach equilibrium. When performing mass scaling,

246 the body forces need to be adjusted to compensate for the scaled density.

Once the mass matrix has been chosen, the DR method gives the following expression for the damping coefficient in terms of the velocity vector, and the stiffness and mass matrices

$$c = 2\sqrt{\frac{\mathbf{V}^T \cdot \mathbf{K} \cdot \mathbf{V}}{\mathbf{V}^T \cdot \mathbf{M} \cdot \mathbf{V}}} \quad , \quad (23)$$

247 where the velocity vector \mathbf{V} is given by the discrete version of $\frac{d\mathbf{U}}{d\tau}$ as obtained from the
248 Newmark method.

Instead of the stiffness matrix \mathbf{K} , a diagonal estimator \mathbf{S} of the stiffness is used in (23) Oakley and Knight Jr (1995), such that

$$S_{ii} = -\frac{R_i^m - R_i^{m-1}}{U_i^m - U_i^{m-1}} = -\frac{R_i^m - R_i^{m-1}}{\Delta\tau V_i^{m-\frac{1}{2}}} \quad . \quad (24)$$

This significantly optimizes the computation of the damping coefficient, which reduces to

$$c = 2\sqrt{\frac{\sum_{i=1}^{n_u} V_i^{m-\frac{1}{2}} (R_i^{m-1} - R_i^m)}{\Delta\tau \sum_{i=1}^{n_u} (V_i^{m-\frac{1}{2}})^2 M_{ii}}} \quad . \quad (25)$$

249 In the preceding equations, $m - \frac{1}{2}$ refers to the predictor value and $\Delta\tau$ is the Newmark-
250 beta integration time step.

251 The mass damping matrix can then be computed as $\mathbf{C} = c\mathbf{M}$. Notice that, unlike
252 \mathbf{M} , \mathbf{C} needs to be updated after every DR step. This choice for the damping matrix
253 guarantees that the mechanical behavior is that of a critically-damped system Oakley
254 and Knight Jr (1995), providing the desired quasi-static response throughout the iterative
255 process. As both the fictitious mass and damping matrices are diagonal, equation (22) is
256 reduced to an uncoupled system of algebraic equations. Additionally, $\mathbf{U}^m \xrightarrow{m \rightarrow \infty} \mathbf{U}^{k+1}$
257 where \mathbf{U}^{k+1} solves equation (21) for a given p_h^{k+1} . Hence, \mathcal{S} is defined as this limit.
258 Alternatively, as in Smilovich et al. (2021), we may define \mathcal{S} as the transient solution to
259 (21) after a finite number N of pseudo-time increments.

260 *3.4. Numerical implementation*

261 The staggered algorithm described in the preceding subsections is implemented in
 262 Y-FRAC[®], a numerical framework for massively-parallel computational mechanics sim-
 263 ulations based on domain partitioning, enabled by the METIS library [Karypis and Kumar](#)
 264 (2009).

265 In terms of how the staggered operator \mathcal{H} has been defined, the iterative procedure
 266 for determining the solution at time $t = t_n$ starts off with $\mathbf{u}_h^0 = \mathbf{u}_h^{t_{n-1}}$, from which w_h^0 is
 267 computed in order to solve for p_h^1 , and so forth.

268 Regarding the initial conditions for the staggered algorithm, solving for $t = t_0$, *i.e.*,
 269 the first step, requires knowledge of $\mathbf{u}_h^0 = \mathbf{u}_h^{t_0}$. The system of equations (19) is well
 270 defined even for an opening field that is identically zero, so we may simply set $w_h^0 \equiv 0$,
 271 and p_h^0 equal to some arbitrary initialization pressure p_0 , which will result in $p_h^1 \approx p_0$.

The criterion for assessing whether convergence has been achieved after iteration k is formulated in terms of the norms of \mathbf{P} and \mathbf{U} . We additionally check the fulfillment of equation (16) up to a certain tolerance. We then have the following conditions for convergence

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \frac{\|\mathbf{P}^k - \mathbf{P}^{k-1}\|_2}{\|\mathbf{P}^{k-1}\|_2} < pTol \quad , \\ \frac{\|\mathbf{U}^k - \mathbf{U}^{k-1}\|_2}{\|\mathbf{U}^{k-1}\|_2} < uTol \quad , \\ \left| \frac{\int_{\partial_I \mathcal{B}_h} \beta^{t_n} \frac{w_h^{t_n} - w_h^{t_{n-1}}}{\Delta t} \, d\Gamma}{\int_{\partial_I \mathcal{B}_h} \beta^{t_n} \left(\mathcal{Q} - \frac{2C_L}{\sqrt{t_n - t_0(\mathbf{x})}} \right) \, d\Gamma} - 1 \right| < sTol \quad . \end{array} \right. \quad (26)$$

As for obtaining \mathbf{P}^k , we make use of the PETSc library [Balay et al. \(2019\)](#) [Balay et al. \(2020\)](#) [Balay et al. \(1997\)](#) in order to solve the linear system of equations (19) in an efficient, parallel manner. Similarly, we determine that \mathbf{U}^k has been obtained from the sequence of DR steps if the following conditions are satisfied for the chosen displacement, velocity, and acceleration relative tolerances, or as mentioned, simply as the result of a

finite number N of pseudo-time increments

$$\begin{cases} \frac{\|\mathbf{U}^m - \mathbf{U}^{m-1}\|_2}{\|\mathbf{U}^{m-1}\|_2} < uTol_{DR} \quad , \\ \frac{\|\mathbf{V}^m - \mathbf{V}^{m-1}\|_2}{\max_{i=1,\dots,m} \|\mathbf{V}^i\|_2} < vTol_{DR} \quad , \\ \frac{\|\mathbf{A}^m - \mathbf{A}^{m-1}\|_2}{\max_{i=1,\dots,m} \|\mathbf{A}^i\|_2} < aTol_{DR} \quad . \end{cases} \quad (27)$$

272 Upon convergence, we update the fluid domain and continue with the next time step.

273 4. Stability and selection of the artificial compressibility

274 As mentioned, split operator techniques in hydraulic fracturing modeling are prone
 275 to exhibiting stability issues [Giovanardi et al. \(2020\)](#) [Matin and Robert \(2019\)](#) [Smilovich](#)
 276 [et al. \(2021\)](#) [Vahab and Khalili \(2019\)](#). In this section we derive stability conditions for
 277 the proposed algorithm, under simplified conditions.

278 4.1. Stability

279 For a non-propagating linear crack embedded in an homogeneous, impermeable linear-
 280 elastic medium under plane-strain conditions, such as the one depicted in Figure 1, the
 281 crack opening w is related to the fluid pressure p through

Figure 1: Non-propagating pressurized linear crack.

$$w(x) = \frac{2}{\pi E'} \int_{-\ell}^{\ell} p(u) \ln \left| \frac{\sqrt{\ell^2 - x^2} + \sqrt{\ell^2 - u^2}}{\sqrt{\ell^2 - x^2} - \sqrt{\ell^2 - u^2}} \right| du \quad , \quad (28)$$

where E' is the plane-strain Young's modulus, and ℓ is the crack half-length. Given the additional hypothesis of a negligible fluid pressure gradient, which results in a uniform pressure distribution, w reads

$$w(x) = \frac{4p\ell}{E'} \sqrt{1 - \left(\frac{x}{\ell}\right)^2} \quad . \quad (29)$$

The continuous in space, discrete in time iterative scheme from section 3 can then be formulated for this particular case as follows

$$\begin{cases} Bp^k = Bp^{k-1} - \frac{w(x)^{k-1} - w(x)^{t_{n-1}}}{\Delta t} + Q\delta(x) \quad , \\ w(x)^k = \frac{4p^k\ell}{E'} \sqrt{1 - \left(\frac{x}{\ell}\right)^2} \quad . \end{cases} \quad (30)$$

In the above equations B is the artificial compressibility, $w(x)^{t_{n-1}}$ the previous, converged, opening distribution, and Q is the injection flow rate. Integrating from $-\ell$ to ℓ yields

$$2\ell B\Delta tp^k = 2\ell B\Delta tp^{k-1} - \int_{-\ell}^{\ell} w(x)^{k-1} dx + \int_{-\ell}^{\ell} w(x)^{t_{n-1}} dx + Q\Delta t \quad (31)$$

which, using (29) and noting that the second integral evaluates to the previous, converged crack volume per unit thickness $V^{t_{n-1}}$, reduces to

$$2\ell B\Delta tp^k = 2\ell B\Delta tp^{k-1} - \frac{2\pi\ell^2}{E'} p^{k-1} + V^{t_{n-1}} + Q\Delta t \quad . \quad (32)$$

The recursive equation for the pressure at iteration k is thus given by

$$p^k = p^{k-1} \left(1 - \frac{\pi\ell}{E'B\Delta t} \right) + \frac{1}{2\ell B\Delta t} (V^{t_{n-1}} + Q\Delta t) \quad . \quad (33)$$

Let $B_0 = \frac{\pi\ell}{E'\Delta t}$. We can then express equation (33) in terms of B_0 and $p^0 = p^{t_{n-1}}$

according to

$$p^k = p^0 \left(1 - \frac{B_0}{B}\right)^k + \frac{1}{2\ell B \Delta t} (V^{t_{n-1}} + Q \Delta t) \sum_{j=0}^{k-1} \left(1 - \frac{B_0}{B}\right)^j . \quad (34)$$

Equation (34) shows that the necessary and sufficient condition for convergence of the sequence $\{p^k\}$ is that $|1 - \frac{B_0}{B}| < 1$, and we thus have a stability condition.

For $B \leq \frac{1}{2}B_0$, the sequence $\{p^k\}$ given by (34) diverges. If $\frac{1}{2}B_0 < B < B_0$, the sequence oscillates since $-1 < 1 - \frac{B_0}{B} < 0$, but it is nonetheless convergent. If $B = B_0$, the solution is obtained immediately from p^0 . Lastly, for $B > B_0$, a convergent monotonically increasing sequence is obtained. Whenever $\{p^k\}$ converges, the convergence can be shown to be linear. Therefore, B_0 is expected to remain a good enough guess for the optimal artificial compressibility when some of the hypotheses that have been established throughout this derivation are dropped. A similar approach can be followed for a radial crack in 3D space.

4.2. Numerical experiments

We now conduct a series of numerical experiments in order to verify the predicted effect of the artificial compressibility on the convergence of the proposed iterative scheme, now for a propagating hydraulic fracture. We choose suitable conditions that mimic those established at the beginning of this section. That is, a hydraulic fracture propagating in a straight line, embedded in an homogeneous, impermeable linear-elastic medium under plane-strain conditions, and a set of solid and fluid properties that lead to a negligible pressure gradient.

Six simulations are then executed. The artificial compressibility is originally set to $B = B_0$ while the fracture propagates with $t < t_{max}$, then, as soon as $t \geq t_{max}$, it is instantaneously modified in order to bring about the different convergence behaviors. That is, divergent, oscillatory, optimal, and monotonically convergent. The initial time t_0 for which the simulations are initialized and t_{max} are respectively taken as 36.0 s and 56.0 s, while the time step Δt is set to 10.0 s. The different values chosen for the artificial

Figure 2: Normalized fluid pressure as a function of the iteration number k for six different values of the artificial compressibility, displaying various convergence behaviors.

306 compressibility are listed in Table 1.

Case	i	ii	iii	iv	v	vi
B/B_0	0.49	0.7	0.8	1.0	2.0	3.0

Table 1: Values for the artificial compressibility.

307 Case i is expected to diverge, while cases ii to vi , to converge. Cases ii and iii should
 308 exhibit oscillatory convergence, while v and vi should converge monotonically, and slower
 309 than iv . Figure 2 shows the fluid pressure p^k relative to the converged pressure p^∞ ,
 310 plotted against the iteration number k corresponding to the first time step for which
 311 $t > t_{max}$.

312 The results agree with the predicted behavior, even though the derivation above was

313 carried out for the semi-discrete problem and the hypotheses mentioned earlier are not
 314 exactly fulfilled, *i.e.*, the pressure gradient may be negligible but not zero. As expected,
 315 $B = B_0$ yields the fastest convergence.

316 5. Verification

317 We now test the proposed algorithm against known analytical solutions in order to
 318 assess its viability.

319 5.1. The KGD problem

320 Consider the case of a hydraulic fracture propagating in a straight line, immersed in
 321 a two-dimensional impermeable linear-elastic medium under plane-strain conditions, and
 322 driven by the constant injection of an incompressible fluid, as illustrated in Figure 3. This
 323 is known as the KGD problem, for which there are several available analytical and semi-
 324 analytical solutions [Garagash \(2000\)](#) [Garagash and Detournay \(2005\)](#), some of which
 325 include the existence of a fluid lag region [Garagash \(2006\)](#), leak-off effects [Adachi and](#)
 326 [Detournay \(2008\)](#), and non-Newtonian rheology [Adachi and Detournay \(2002\)](#), among
 327 several others.

Figure 3: KGD crack with related quantities.

328 Given these conditions, the solution can be shown to depend exclusively on two
 329 dimensionless groups [Garagash \(2006\)](#), which in turn depend on the elastic modulus E ,

330 the Poisson ratio ν , the fracture toughness K_{Ic} , the remote confining stress σ_0 , the time
 331 t , the injection rate Q_0 , and the fluid dynamic viscosity μ . We avoid repeating numerical
 332 factors by introducing $E' = \frac{E}{1-\nu^2}$, $K' = 4 \left(\frac{2}{\pi}\right)^{1/2} K_{Ic}$, and $\mu' = 12\mu$.

The solution is characterized by the crack opening profile $w(x, t)$, the net pressure distribution $p(x, t)$, the crack half-length $\ell(t)$, and the fluid-filled crack half-length $\ell_f(t)$. We are only interested in solutions for which $\ell(t)$ equals $\ell_f(t)$, *i.e.*, such that we can neglect the fluid lag. Under this assumption the number of dimensionless groups reduces to a single one, which in the so-called viscosity scaling is the dimensionless toughness \mathcal{K} , given by

$$\mathcal{K} = K' \left(\frac{1}{E'^3 Q_0 \mu'} \right)^{1/4} . \quad (35)$$

For this particular scaling, to which we associate the subscript m , we have the following expressions for the crack opening, the net pressure, and the crack half-length

$$\begin{aligned} w(x, t) &= \epsilon_m(t) L_m(t) \Omega_m(\xi(x), \mathcal{K}) \quad , \\ p(x, t) &= \epsilon_m(t) E' \Pi_m(\xi(x), \mathcal{K}) \quad , \\ \ell(t) &= L_m(t) \gamma_m(\mathcal{K}) \quad , \end{aligned} \quad (36)$$

in terms of the small parameter $\epsilon_m(t)$, the length scale $L_m(t)$, and the crack coordinate ξ

$$\begin{aligned} \epsilon_m(t) &= \left(\frac{\mu'}{E' t} \right)^{1/3} \quad , \\ L_m(t) &= \left(\frac{E'^{1/4} Q_0^{3/4} t}{\mu'^{1/4}} \right)^{2/3} \quad , \\ \xi &= \frac{x}{\ell(t)}, \quad 0 \leq \xi \leq 1 \quad , \end{aligned} \quad (37)$$

where Ω_m , Π_m , and γ_m are the dimensionless crack opening, the dimensionless net pressure, and the dimensionless crack half-length, respectively. Similarly, in the toughness scaling the governing parameter is the dimensionless viscosity \mathcal{M}

$$\mathcal{M} = \frac{E'^3 Q_0 \mu'}{K'^4} \quad , \quad (38)$$

which is related to the dimensionless toughness according to $\mathcal{K} = \mathcal{M}^{-1/4}$. In this scaling, referred to by the subscript k , the solution may be expressed as

$$\begin{aligned} w(x, t) &= \epsilon_k(t) L_k(t) \Omega_k(\xi(x), \mathcal{M}) \quad , \\ p(x, t) &= \epsilon_k(t) E' \Pi_k(\xi(x), \mathcal{M}) \quad , \\ \ell(t) &= L_k(t) \gamma_k(\mathcal{M}) \quad , \end{aligned} \tag{39}$$

for Ω_k , Π_k , and γ_k the dimensionless crack opening, net pressure, and crack half-length in the toughness scaling, respectively, while $\epsilon_k(t)$ and $L_k(t)$ are given by

$$\begin{aligned} \epsilon_k(t) &= \left(\frac{K'^4}{E'^4 Q_0 t} \right)^{1/3} \quad , \\ L_k(t) &= \left(\frac{E' Q_0 t}{K'} \right)^{2/3} \quad . \end{aligned} \tag{40}$$

333 Two main energy dissipation mechanisms can be identified. When $\mathcal{K} \ll 1$ the domi-
 334 nant mechanism is that of the viscous fluid flow. Alternatively, when $\mathcal{K} \gg 1$ the energy
 335 input is mainly consumed in the fracturing of the solid. The asymptotics corresponding
 336 to $\mathcal{K} = 0$ and $\mathcal{K} = \infty$ are dubbed the zero-toughness solution and the infinite-toughness
 337 solution. The zero-toughness asymptotic approximates the solution well enough for
 338 $\mathcal{K} \lesssim 0.37$, while for $\mathcal{K} \gtrsim 4.13$, the infinite-toughness solution results in an excellent
 339 approximation [Garagash \(2000\)](#). The asymptotic solutions may be obtained by setting
 340 $\Omega_m(\xi, 0) \approx 1.133$, $\Pi_m(\xi, 0) \approx 0.544$, $\gamma_m(0) \approx 0.616$ in [\(36\)](#), and $\Omega_k(\xi, 0) = \pi^{-1/3}$,
 341 $\Pi_k(\xi, 0) = \frac{1}{8}\pi^{1/3}$, $\gamma_k(0) = 2\pi^{-2/3}$ in [\(40\)](#) [Detournay \(2004\)](#).

342 5.2. Verification for the KGD problem

343 Two sets of parameters producing dimensionless toughness values corresponding to
 344 each limiting regime are chosen. These, along with various simulation parameters are
 345 listed in [Tables 2 and 3](#). The resulting dimensionless toughness values fall well within
 346 the ranges for which the asymptotic solutions result in very good approximations.

347 As the problem exhibits symmetry we only consider half of the domain. Adequate

348 boundary conditions are imposed along the symmetry edge, namely zero normal displace-
 349 ments, while the inlet flow rate is taken as half of the total flow rate Q_0 .

Case	viscosity	toughness
\mathcal{K}	0.317	5.031
E	1.0e10 Pa	2.17e8 Pa
ν	0.2	0.2
G_c	4.93e2 Pa · m	4.93e2 Pa · m
σ_0	9.0e6 Pa	0.0 Pa
Q_0	1.99e-1 m ² /s	1.45e-4 m ² /s
μ	0.1 Pa · s	0.1 Pa · s

Table 2: The set of physical parameters used in the KGD simulations. The first case corresponds to the viscosity-dominated propagation regime, while the second one falls within the toughness-dominated regime.

Case	viscosity	toughness
ℓ_0	1.0 m	1.0 m
ℓ_{max}	30.0 m	30.0 m
N_e	12, 120	17, 826
h	8.3e-2 m	6.25e-2 m
$pTol$	1.0e-5	1.0e-5
$uTol$	1.0e-5	1.0e-5
$sTol$	1.0e-2	1.0e-2
N	100	100

Table 3: Some relevant simulation parameters: the initial length at which the simulation begins, the final length for which it terminates, the number of bulk elements, and a measure of the interface element size along the propagation path. The time increment is chosen so as to produce a constant length increment of about the size of one interface element per time step. The first coupled step is fed a larger time step value that serves as an initialization time. Lastly, the tolerances from (26) and (27), and the number of dynamic relaxation steps per coupled iteration.

350 The numerical results are contrasted against the analytical solutions for the crack
 351 half-length, the inlet crack opening, and the fluid pressure at the injection point, as
 352 given by (36) for $x = 0$. These results are shown in Figures 4 and 5.

353 A favorable comparison is observed between the simulations and the corresponding
 354 analytical solutions. Early time discrepancies, as evidenced in Figure 6, are likely due
 355 to the way in which the simulations are initialized, as the computation of the opening
 356 time derivative during the first coupled step is performed with a previous opening field

Figure 4: Results for the viscosity-dominated propagation regime of a KGD hydraulic fracture.

357 that is identically nil. The opening field corresponding to an artificial previous time
 358 step could be fed to the model in order to have a more accurate, even exact, opening
 359 time derivative computation. Similarly, the initial conditions could be set from the exact
 360 solution corresponding to the initial length ℓ_0 .

361 After a number of time steps the influence of the initial conditions seems to wane.
 362 Further deviations from the exact solutions may be explained as due to effects related to
 363 the existence of a cohesive zone, which breaks the self-similarity that characterizes the
 364 analytical solutions [Garagash \(2000\)](#) [Garagash and Detournay \(2005\)](#). Additionally, the
 365 fact that the fluid domain is kept fixed while the crack propagates results in artificial,
 366 numerical fluid lag.

Figure 5: Results for the toughness-dominated propagation regime of a KGD hydraulic fracture.

Figure 6: Relative errors for the KGD simulations. Both the opening and the pressure refer to the inlet values.

367 5.3. Penny-shaped crack

368 Now consider a penny-shaped fluid-driven fracture propagating in an impermeable
 369 linear-elastic medium, where the incompressible fracturing fluid is injected at a constant
 370 rate, as exemplified in Figure 7.

Figure 7: Transverse section of a penny-shaped crack with related quantities.

Similarly to the KGD problem, the dimensionless toughness for a penny-shaped fracture can be written as [Savitski and Detournay \(2002\)](#)

$$\mathcal{K} = K' \left(\frac{t^2}{E'^{13} Q_0^3 \mu'^5} \right)^{1/18} . \quad (41)$$

371 It is evident from the time dependency of the dimensionless toughness that as the
 372 fracture evolves it will transition from a viscosity-dominated propagation regime ($\mathcal{K} \lesssim 1$)
 373 to a toughness-dominated one ($\mathcal{K} \gtrsim 3.5$). Fracture propagation will generally occur
 374 in the viscosity-dominated regime for typical field operation values of the intervening
 375 parameters [Savitski and Detournay \(2002\)](#).

The zero-toughness solution is given in the viscosity-scaling by the following set of equations

$$\begin{aligned} w(r, t) &= \epsilon_m(t) L_m(t) \Omega_m(\rho(r), 0) \quad , \\ p(r, t) &= \epsilon_m(t) E' \Pi_m(\rho(r), 0) \quad , \\ R(t) &= L_m(t) \gamma_m(0) \quad , \end{aligned} \quad (42)$$

where $w(\rho, t)$ is the crack opening, $R(t)$ the crack radius, and $p(\rho, t)$ the net fluid pressure. The small parameter $\epsilon_m(t)$, the length scale $L_m(t)$, and ρ can be expressed as

$$\begin{aligned}\epsilon_m(t) &= \left(\frac{\mu'}{E't}\right)^{1/3}, \\ L_m(t) &= \left(\frac{E'Q_0^3 t^4}{\mu'}\right)^{1/9}, \\ \rho &= \frac{r}{R(t)}, \quad 0 \leq \rho \leq 1,\end{aligned}\tag{43}$$

while the dimensionless crack opening and the dimensionless crack radius take the values $\Omega_m(\rho, 0) \approx 1.197$ and $\gamma_m(0) \approx 0.696$ [Detournay \(2004\)](#). Although for the zero-toughness solution the dimensionless pressure $\Pi_m(\rho, 0)$ is singular at both $\rho = 0$ and $\rho = 1$, so $p(0, t)$ and $p(R, t)$ remain undefined, it can be integrated in $[0, 1]$. Hence we may define the average pressure as

$$\bar{p}(t) = \epsilon_m(t)E'\bar{\Pi}_m(0),\tag{44}$$

where the average dimensionless pressure $\bar{\Pi}_m(0)$ is given by

$$\bar{\Pi}_m(0) = \frac{1}{\pi} \int_0^{2\pi} \int_0^1 \Pi_m(\rho, 0) \rho \, d\rho \, d\phi \approx 0.476.\tag{45}$$

376 5.4. Verification for a penny-shaped crack

377 A set of physical parameters resulting in a dimensionless toughness value that remains
378 within the limit corresponding to the viscosity-dominated propagation regime throughout
379 the entire simulation is chosen. Tables 4 and 5 list these as well as several simulation
380 parameters.

381 Similarly, as the problem exhibits symmetry we are able to consider only a quarter-
382 domain. Zero-normal-displacement boundary conditions are imposed along the two sym-
383 metry planes. The inlet flow rate is again taken as a quarter the total flow rate Q_0 .

384 The results are compared against the analytical solutions for the crack radius, the
385 inlet crack opening, and the average fluid pressure, respectively given by (42) for $r = 0$,

Case	penny-shaped
E	1.0e10 Pa
ν	0.2
G_c	4.93e2 Pa · m
σ_0	10.0e6 Pa
Q_0	1.99e-1 m ³ /s
μ	1.0 Pa · s

Table 4: The set of physical parameters used in the penny-shaped crack.

Case	penny-shaped
R_0	1.0 m
R_{max}	10.0 m
N_e	47, 931
h	1.66e-1 m
$pTol$	1.0e-4
$uTol$	1.0e-4
$sTol$	1.0e-2
N	100

Table 5: Some relevant simulation parameters for the penny-shaped crack. The time increment is again chosen so as to produce a constant radius increment of about the size of one interface element per time step

386 and (44). The results are shown in Figure 8, yielding a reasonable agreement, with most
387 deviations likely being caused by numerical fluid lag and cohesive zone effects. Figure
388 9 depicts the relative error for the inlet opening, the average pressure, and the crack
389 radius.

(a) Crack radius.

(b) Average pressure.

(c) Inlet crack opening.

Figure 8: Results for a penny-shaped crack.

Figure 9: Relative errors for a penny-shaped crack. The opening refers to the inlet value, while the pressure refers to the spatially-averaged value.

390 **6. Conclusions**

391 A staggered algorithm for the simulation of hydraulic fracturing processes under zero-
392 lag conditions is presented. An explicit Dynamic Relaxation technique with mass scaling
393 is chosen as an efficient solution method for solving the solid equilibrium equations. The
394 fluid pressure field is periodically updated, as obtained from the pseudo-transient mass
395 conservation equation for a fixed domain.

396 The addition of a pseudo-transient term allows the prescription of full Neumann
397 boundary conditions, circumventing ill-posedness and nonuniqueness of the solution,
398 while also removing the need to resort to additional iterative loops that would inevitably
399 arise from the imposition of intermediate pressure boundary conditions.

400 Stability and convergence aspects are analyzed for a particular case under simplified
401 conditions, for which an optimal artificial compressibility value is derived. It is assumed
402 that in more complex simulations, acceptable values of the artificial compressibility may
403 be derived in a similar way.

404 Verification against several known analytical solutions demonstrates the feasibility
405 of the proposed algorithm, which can be readily implemented in essentially any finite
406 elements code for hydraulic fracture propagation.

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